

Supplement D (ODD+D protocol)

HomininWaterCrossingABM v1.1.0

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ODD + D Protocol

We provide a technical description of the model by applying the ODD + D protocol, which was originally developed by Grimm et al. (2010) and later extended by Müller et al. (2013) for models of human decision making.

Overview

The model is an updated version of the model introduced by Hölzchen et al. (2021), which we extended by integrating geographic maps, predefining behavioral scenarios and further visualizations.

Purpose

The model simulates the crossing of a water barrier by agents representing hominins. It is designed to quantitatively test the chance of agents crossing a water barrier on either an artificial or geographical map. The agents can be assigned with different modes of movement across the water ranging from undirected paddling to basic rafting.

Entities, state variables and scales

On the one hand, the environment of the model consists of a grid of cells, which we refer to as “patches”. These patches belong either to the source area, the water barrier, islands or to

the target area. On the other hand, we refer to the mobile entities as “agents”. The agents represent hominin individuals. All parameters of the environment are listed and described in Table 1, all parameters of the agents are described in Table 2. Visualization parameters are listed in Table 3. These determine what is visible in the simulation view and have no effect on the simulation results. The function of the button in the interface are listed in Table 4.

Table 1. Environment and patch parameters

Name	Type of parameter	Description
<i>current-scenario</i>	factor	current scenario, e.g., uniform, random-dynamic or from-map (reconstructed)
<i>uniform-current-speed</i>	factor	speed of the water current; default level = zero;
<i>uniform-current-direction</i>	factor	direction of the water current in degrees; default level = 90
<i>is-source-area?</i>	factor	True = patch belongs to source area; False = patch does not belong to source area
<i>is-target-area?</i>	factor	True = patch belongs to target area; False = patch does not belong to target area
<i>local-current-direction</i>	response	current direction of the patch
<i>local-current-speed</i>	response	current speed of the patch
<i>local-water-temperature</i>	response	water temperature of the patch
<i>min-resources</i>	constant	minimum level of resource qualities = 0
<i>patch-type</i>	factor	type of the patch (e.g. “land”, “water”)
<i>pcolor</i>	response	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the color of the patch which is determined by the map coloring factor (<i>map-coloring</i>)
<i>plabel</i>	factor	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the label text of the patch; not used in the present model
<i>plabel-color</i>	factor	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the color of the label of the patch; not used in the present model
<i>pxcor</i>	response	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the x-position of the patch on the map

<i>pycor</i>	response	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the y-position of the patch on the map
<i>resources</i>	factor	resource-qualities of the patch
<i>slope</i>	factor	slope of the patch in percent rise
<i>time-occupied</i>	response	cumulative number of ticks in which the patch was occupied by agents
<i>water-barrier-size</i>	factor	extent of the water barrier
<i>water-temperature-interval</i>	factor	temperature of the water
<i>water-temperature-offset</i>	factor	water temperature offset, e.g. -5°C or + 5°C
<i>water-temperature-scenario</i>	factor	water temperature scenario, e.g., uniform or from-map (reconstructed)

Table 2. Agent parameters

Name	Type of parameter	Description
<i>action</i>	response	action of the agent, e.g. “water-movement” or “land-movement”
<i>actual-patch</i>	response	holds whether the current patch of the agent is in the source area, water or target area; required for counting the crossing attempts
<i>basal-metabolic-rate</i>	factor	basal metabolic rate per day; default level = 1500 energy-units/day
<i>breed</i>	constant	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the breed of the agent; breed = hominins
<i>color</i>	constant	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the color of the agent; color = red
<i>constant-population-size</i>	factor	switch on for agents who disappear being replaced by new agents in the source area, off for no replacement; default level = On; This factor is not varied in the previous experiments and is intended for future applications.
<i>current-speed</i>	factor	speed of the water current; default level = zero
<i>death-rate-in-water</i>	factor	probability with which agents in the water die of random causes
<i>decision-randomness</i>	factor	randomness of decision; default level = 0.1

<i>dehydration</i>	factor	switch on for dehydration, off for no effect of dehydration; default level = On; This factor is not varied in the previous experiments and is intended for future applications.
<i>effective-movement-distance</i>	response	effective movement distance calculated from slope (see section "Movement behavior and survival of the agents")
<i>energy</i>	response	current energy in kcal
<i>energy-loss-swimming</i>	constant	loss of energy when paddling or swimming default level = 800 kcal
<i>fleeing-probability</i>	factor	probability with which the agent flees, when the level of resource qualities of the local patch is below the threshold of fleeing (<i>fleeing-threshold</i>); This factor is not yet tested in previous experiment and is intended for future applications.; default level = 0 (no effect)
<i>fleeing-threshold</i>	factor	level of resource qualities in which fleeing is possible; This factor is not yet tested in previous experiment and is intended for future applications.; default level = 0 (no effect)
<i>heading</i>	response	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the direction of movement of the agent
<i>hidden?</i>	constant	built-in NetLogo variable which allows switching the visualization of agents on or off; hidden? = False (agents are visible)
<i>hours-until-dehydration</i>	factor	duration in hours in which the agent survives without access to freshwater; default level = 96 hours
<i>hours-spent-in-water</i>	response	duration in hours the agent spent in water; is reset to zero, if the agents returns onto a land patch
<i>hypothermia</i>	factor	switch on for swimming, on for rafting
<i>label</i>	constant	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the label text of the agent; label = "" (no label)

<i>label-color</i>	constant	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the color of the label: label-color = black; labels are not used in the model
<i>max-energy</i>	factor	maximum energy default = 45,000 energy-units
<i>max-fleeing-pioneering-distance</i>	factor	maximum distance of target patch, when fleeing or pioneering; default level = 99 km
<i>max-hominins</i>	response	maximum number of agents which is calculated from the density of agents (<i>population-density</i>)
<i>movement-in-water-direction</i>	factor	direction of movement in water; default level = "random"
<i>new-founder?</i>	response	True = member of a founder group; False = not a member of any founder group
<i>not-hydrated-ticks</i>	response	number of ticks without freshwater since the last entering in the water
<i>number-founder-agents</i>	factor	required number for a founder group; default level = 50
<i>optimal-walking-speed</i>	constant	maximum speed of movement on land = 5 km/h
<i>pen-mode</i>	constant	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the mode of the mark of the agent; not used in the present model
<i>pen-size</i>	constant	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the size of the mark of the agent, when <i>pen-down</i> is activated; not used in the present model
<i>perception-radius</i>	factor	radius of perception; default level = 20 km
<i>pioneering-probability</i>	factor	probability with which the agent pioneers, when the level of resource qualities of the local patch is above the threshold of pioneering (<i>pioneering-threshold</i>); This factor is not yet tested in previous experiment and is intended for future applications.; default level = 0 (no effect)
<i>pioneering-threshold</i>	factor	level of resource qualities in which pioneering is possible; This factor is not yet tested in

		previous experiment and is intended for future applications.; default level = 1 (no effect)
<i>population-density</i>	factor	density of agents on the map; default level = 0.1 individuals/km ²
<i>previous-patch</i>	response	holds whether the previous patch of the agent was in the source area, water or target area; required for counting the crossing attempts
<i>reached-target-area?</i>	response	True = reached the target area; False = not reached the target area
<i>remove-old-population</i>	factor	switch on for removal of founder groups, off for not removing them
<i>shape</i>	constant	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the shape of the agent; shape = "dot"
<i>size</i>	constant	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the size of the agent visualization; size = 2
<i>target-patch</i>	response	patch towards the agent heads
<i>target-patch-duration</i>	response	duration in ticks a target-patch is aimed at; if the value reaches zero, a new target-patch is selected
<i>who</i>	response	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the ID of the agent
<i>xcor</i>	response	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the x-position of the agent on the map
<i>ycor</i>	response	built-in NetLogo variable which holds the y-position of the agent on the map

Table 3. Visualization parameters

Name	Type of parameter	Description
<i>arrow-density</i>	factor	density of current arrows, if <i>show-current-directions</i> is pressed
<i>arrow-size</i>	factor	size of current arrows, if <i>show-current-directions</i> is pressed
<i>autosave-video</i>	factor	True = video of the simulation is saved automatically when <i>ticks = video-duration-in-ticks</i>

<i>draw-crossing-path</i>	factor	True = draws movement paths of agents; False = no movement paths are drawn
<i>heatmap-output</i>	factor	True = heatmap is automatically saved to an *.asc file; False = heatmap is not saved
<i>land-coloring</i>	factor	holds which terrestrial map type is visualized, e.g, slope, resources or time occupied
<i>skull-duration</i>	factor	duration in ticks a skull is displayed where an agent died
<i>visualization</i>	factor	holds how the simulation is visualized
<i>water-coloring</i>	factor	holds which water map type is visualized, e.g., water temperature, current speed, current direction or time occupied

Table 4. Buttons

Name	Description
<i>default-settings</i>	resets the factor levels to default settings
<i>export-map</i>	exports the map which is selected in <i>to-be-exported-map</i>
<i>go</i>	runs the simulation until <i>max-simulation-duration</i> is reached
<i>profiler</i>	runs the profiler for performance tests
<i>reset-recorder</i>	resets the video record
<i>save-recording</i>	saves the recorded video to a mp4 file
<i>setup</i>	calls the <i>setup</i> procedure
<i>show source patches</i>	shows the source patches in yellow
<i>show target patches</i>	shows the target patches in brown
<i>show-current-directions</i>	displays arrows indicating the current directions; arrow visualization is defined by <i>arrow-density</i> and <i>arrow-size</i>
<i>start-recorder</i>	starts video recording
<i>step</i>	runs only a single tick of the simulation
<i>update-movement-scenario</i>	updates the factor levels according to the selected <i>movement-scenario</i>
<i>update-visualization</i>	updates the visualization and needs to be pressed for applying the changes in <i>land-coloring</i> or <i>water-coloring</i>

A patch represents 1 km² of real space and 1 time step, which we refer to as „tick“

represents 1 hour of real time.

Process overview and scheduling

At the beginning of each *tick*, the number of agents is maintained, when *constant-population-size* is enabled. During a simulation run, agents may die if they move in the water (see section “Submodels”) or leave the map at the border, either on land or in the water. In the case of disappearance, new agents will be randomly placed onto the source area of the map until the set density of the agents (*population-density*) is met. Then, the agents move across the landscape (see section “Individual Decision-Making”).

Design Concepts

Theoretical and Empirical Background

The environment of the model is a simplified representation of a landscape being divided by a water barrier or a reconstructed geographic map. Here, we define a crossing as a movement from a source area towards a target area on the opposite shore across the water barrier. The movement on land of the agents is controlled by the range of perception (*perception-radius*) of resource qualities of surrounding patches within this radius. This includes resource qualities of the opposite shore, if these are within the range of perception. Furthermore, the movement is controlled by a degree of randomness (*decision-randomness*) of decision (see “Individual Decision-Making” section). The model allows adapting different modes of movement across the water, which we assume for hominins who did not possess advanced skills in maritime navigation. Moreover, the modes of movement define the degree to which the agents will be affected by factors of physiology (see section “Submodels”) and factors of the water barrier (see section “Environment” in “Submodels”).

Individual Decision-Making

The agents attempt to cross the water by applying a set of movement modes which are determined by the factors directionality (*movement-in-water-direction*), speed in water (*water-movement-speed*), energetic demand (*energy-loss-swimming*), hypothermia (*hypothermia*) and thermoregulation (*thermoregulation*). By these a variety of movement modes can be defined. The model, moreover, contains a set of pre-defined behavioral scenarios (Table 5).

Table 5. Pre-defined behavioral scenarios

Scenario					
Directionality	None	None	Directed	Directed	Directed
Submerged	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No
Speed in water [km/h]	0	0	1.5	2	3
Energetic demand [energy-units/h]	0	0	0	800	383
Thermoregulation	On	Off	On	On	Off
Hypothermia	On	Off	On	On	Off

Scenario A represents passive drifting, Scenario B passive rafting, C hitch riding, D directed swimming and E directed rafting (Source: Hölzchen et al., 2022).

The movement on land is determined by resource qualities of the patches and the randomness of decision (*decision-randomness*) of the agents. The agents move on land by selecting a target patch within their range of perception (*perception-radius*) and heading towards it. The degree to which an agent selects the patch with the highest resource qualities within its range of perception, is defined by the randomness of decision (*decision-randomness*). This prevents the agent from getting stuck in local maxima of resource qualities. The speed of the movement on land is controlled by the factor of optimal speed of movement on land (*optimal-walking-speed*), which is 5 km/h by default. Moreover, the speed of movement is modulated by the topography, which is represented by slope, whereat the maximum speed of movement is applied when the slope level is 0%, and the slowest speed of movement is applied at a slope level of 100%. To prevent agents from getting stuck on the map in the case of slope values close to 100%, we limit the slowest speed to 1% of the optimal speed, which results in a minimum speed of movement of 0,05 km/h. We therefore assume that agents are substantially obstructed in movement at slope angles beyond 45°.

In contrast, the movement in water is resulting from the set behavioral scenario (Fig 1). Here, the movement is defined by the scenario specific mode of movement (Table 5) and the extent to which the current of the water deflects the movement (see section “Environment” in “Submodels”).

Fig 1. Behavioral decision tree of the agents. (Source: Hölzchen et al., 2022).

Learning

In the present version of the models, the agents do not learn.

Individual Sensing

The agents perceive resource qualities of the patches within the set radius of perception (*perception-radius*). By default, this is 20 km, which is approximately the distance between Gibraltar and northern Africa. Under good weather conditions it is possible to see Gibraltar from the northern African shore due to the geographical characteristics. To allow for erroneous assessments of resource qualities, we introduced a factor of randomness (*decision-randomness*) in the model, which determines the percentage of incorrectly assessed resource qualities. In this case, the agent selects any patch within its radius of perception, instead of targeting the patch with the highest resource quality.

Stochasticity

The distribution of environmental patch values (resource qualities and slope) is random across the land patches, if any of the random map scenarios is chosen (e.g., “random100x100” or “random200x200”). Moreover, initial agents and new agents appear across the source area randomly. Target patch selection by the agents is probabilistic, with a higher probability for patches with higher resource qualities. We introduced a factor for random death (*death-rate-in-water*) which determines the percentage of agents in the water who die by random causes.

Observation

The model allows for various analyses of responses (Table 6). These responses can either be measured at each tick, or at the end of a simulation run.

Table 6 Model responses

Name	Description
<i>attempts-source-water</i>	total number of crossing attempts by individual agents
<i>attempts-source-water-founder</i>	total number of crossing attempts by groups of individuals of the size of a founder group (<i>number-founder-agents</i>)
<i>crossing-success-rate-individuals</i>	crossing success rate when assuming each individual agent to be a sufficient founder group (<i>number-of-founder-agents</i>) = 1
<i>crossing-success-rate-founder-population (CSR)</i>	crossing success rate of founder groups which is calculated from the crossing attempts by founder groups (<i>attempts-source-water-founder</i>) divided by the total number of successful crossings (<i>sum-of-founder-population-size-reached</i>)
<i>death-dehydration</i>	total number of agents who died from dehydration
<i>death-exhaustion</i>	total number of agents who died from exhaustion
<i>death-hypothermia</i>	total number of agents who died from hypothermia
<i>death-left_map_land</i>	total number of agents who left the map via a land border

<i>death-left_map_water</i>	total number of agents who left the map via a water border
<i>death-random</i>	total number of agents who died randomly
<i>founder-population-size-reached</i>	Boolean response which is 0, when no founder group is establishing in the present tick, and is 1, when a founder group is establishing
<i>mean-individual-hours-water-crossing</i>	mean number of hours required for successful crossings of the water in the present tick
<i>sum-mean-hours-water-crossing</i>	cumulative number of mean hours required for a successful crossing of the water
<i>sum-of-death</i>	sum of deaths by all death causes and map exits
<i>sum-of-founder-population-size-reached</i>	cumulative number of successful establishing of founder groups
<i>sum-of-target-area-hominins</i>	cumulative number of agents in the target area
<i>target-area-hominins</i>	number of agents in the target area in the present tick
<i>thermoregulation-energy-loss-per-hour</i>	loss of energy in energy-units by thermoregulation in the present tick
<i>water-temperature</i>	water temperature in °C in the present tick; is only valid if uniform water temperature is set "uniform"

Details

Implementation Details

The model has been implemented in NetLogo 6.2 (Wilensky, 1999).

Initialization

The configuration of the environment is determined by the selected map scenario (*map-scenario*). In the case a random map scenario (e.g., *random100x100* or *random200x200*), further environmental factors need to be determined to set the size of the water barrier (*water-barrier-size*), water temperature (*water-temperature-interval*) and the properties of the current (*current-scenario*, *uniform-current-speed*, *uniform-current-direction*). If a geographic map scenario is selected, the water barrier is determined by the extent of the

water in the map. If using a geographic map, the factors for water temperature and properties of the currents can be either set uniformly or retrieved from the map (see factors *water-temperature-scenario* and *current-scenario*), whereas the factors for land are retrieved from the respective maps for slope and resource quality. Moreover, the color visualization of the patches is set by the factor *map-coloring*, the duration of the simulation by the factor *max-simulation-duration* and the random seed by the factor *seed*. The default levels of the aforementioned factors are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Default levels of factors for initialization

Name	Description
<i>map-coloring</i>	coloring of the map = “resource qualities” (green color scale)
<i>map-scenario</i>	configuration of the map = “random100x100” (random distribution of slope- and resource qualities levels within land patches)
<i>max-simulation-duration</i>	duration of a single run of the simulation = 2160 hours (90 days)
<i>seed</i>	seed number for built-in NetLogo procedure <i>random-seed</i> ; default-level = 1000

Submodels

Hypothermia

Hypothermia is broadly defined by a core temperature of less than 35°C (Danzl, 2002). The survival time in water increases exponentially with increasing water temperature (Tarlochan and Ramesh, 2005).

Agents in the model die by hypothermia, when they remain in cold water for a certain amount of time.

We developed an equation based on Wittmers and Savage (Wittmers and Savage, 2001), that approximates survival time as a function of cooling rate and water temperature:

$$C_{hour} = -0.095 \cdot T_w + 2.975 \quad (2)$$

, where C_{hour} is the cooling rate in Celsius per hour, and T_w is the water temperature in Celsius (Fig 2).

Fig 2. Equation for calculating the cooling rate as a factor of water temperature. The “X” marks the data points obtained from Wittmers and Savage (Wittmers and Savage, 2001).

The agents on land possess a body temperature (*body-temperature*) of 37°C. When an agent enters the water, the body temperature is reduced by applying equation (1). An agent dies from hypothermia, when the body temperature reaches 30°C (Hayward et al., 1975). When an agent returns onto a land patch, the body temperature is restored to 37°C.

Energy loss

Initially, each agent is equipped with an energy storage which is 45,000 energy-units (*max-energy*) by default. In the water, the agents loose energy by their basal metabolic rate

(*basal-metabolic-rate*), their water movement activity (*energy-loss-water-movement*) and by thermoregulation. For the basal metabolic rate and energy loss from moving in water, the respective factor levels are subtracted from the energy.

Additionally, to model the energy loss by thermoregulation as a function of water temperature and time, we modified the formula by Hayward et al. (Hayward et al., 1975) to a hourly scale:

$$H_h = (4.19 - 0.11T_w) \cdot 60 \quad (1)$$

, where H_h is the energy loss from thermoregulation in energy-units per hour and T_w is the water temperature in degrees Celsius.

An agent dies when its energy reaches zero. If an agent survives the movement in the water and reaches a land patch, its energy is restored to its maximum level (*max-energy*).

Environment

The environment of the model is a grid, where one patch represents 1 km². Patches are either water patches or land patches. The land patches consist of layers for resource qualities and topography represented by slope. The levels of resource qualities range between 0 and 1, whereas a low value (closer to 0) refers to an unfavorable patch and a high value (closer to 1) to a favorable patch. Consequently, the resource qualities of patches perceived by the agents affect their direction of movement on land (see section “Individual Decision-Making” and “Individual Sensing”). Additionally, the slope affects the speed of movement (see “Individual Decision-Making”).

The water temperature determines the intensity of hypothermia (see section “Hypothermia”) and thermoregulation (see section “Energy loss”), whereas the speed and

direction of currents affect the speed and direction of the movement across the water by adding the speed and direction to the movement of the agent, which results in a deflection of the original movement.

The model allows to choose between artificial and geographic map scenarios. In the map scenarios “random100x100” an artificial map is generated with random values of resource qualities and slope of the patches and uniform water temperature and uniform or random dynamic current properties. The size of the map is 100 km x 100 km and the water barrier runs horizontally across the center of the map. Scenario “random200x200” only differs by it’s map size of 200 km x 200 km. Geographic maps that can be selected are for the Gibraltar Strait in the Last Interglacial (“GibraltarStraitLIG”), the Gibraltar Strait in the Last Glacial Maximum (“GibraltarStraitLGM”), the Sicily Strait during the Last Interglacial (“SicilyStraitLIG”), the Sicily Strait in the Last Glacial Maximum (“SicilyStraitLGM”), the Bab-al-Mandab Strait in the Last Interglacial (“BabAlMandabLIG”) and the Bab-al-Mandab Strait in the Last Glacial Maximum (“BabAlMandabLGM”).

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